

CURSING AS A PART OF UKRAINIAN CONFLICT TALK

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Abstract

This study surveys the peculiar characteristics of cursing speech acts in the Ukrainian language by examining different groups of examples. The article answers three questions concerning the role and functions of cursing in conflict talk; culture-bound peculiarities of Ukrainian curses; expressive means that are used to enhance the effect of a cursing utterance. Throughout the study it has been shown that the Ukrainian language is rich in curse expressions uttered in conflict situations as a sign of anger, hatred, irritation or unfair treatment. It has been proved that most Ukrainian curses are closely connected to country's culture, traditions, customs, history, mythology, superstitions and religion. The article also suggests that communicative functions of cursing formulas are understood from the context in which they are said and are practically unlimited: they can vary from emotional and therapeutic to manipulative and influential. The major peculiarity of most Ukrainian curses is their expressiveness. To make a curse sound more persuasive a curser may use various means of expressiveness. The study concludes with the discussion of the potential benefits of cultural approach to analyzing human speech behavior for the purpose to give a more complete understanding of important aspects of the language and way of thinking of the people.

Key words: conflict talk, cursing speech act, national speech behavior, communicative function, expressive means.

1. Introduction

During the last decades, linguistic studies have been devoted to various aspects of human speech behaviour. In this regard, theorists mark a significant increase in the number of research issues that are made towards the investigation of ethnic, age, gender and professional speech behavior of different cultural communities. National speech behavior is interpreted here as a set of norms and traditions of communication accepted in a certain lingual and cultural community. A detailed analysis of the characteristics of national speech behavior is valuable in many ways – linguistic, psycholinguistic, ethnolinguistic, cultural, didactic and pedagogical.

Different cultures are likely to present different language performance; each native speaker acquires his linguistic competence within a sociocultural context. In this aspect, the study of peculiarities of conflict speech genre of cursing provides a more complete understanding of cultural communication laws, strategies and tactics. On the one hand, cursing is a common speech act seen in many languages. On the other hand, it is never chaotic or random; it is always meaningful, rule-governed and culture-bound. Native speakers acquire these communicative rules as they learn language. Thus, somebody's cursing is determined by a peculiar language, familial and cultural environment. Cursing formulas reveal many important aspects of the language, culture and way of thinking of the people.

This article is carried out owing to the fact that a few studies have been done on the issue of cursing conflict speech acts in the Ukrainian language. Therefore, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the role and functions of cursing in conflict talk?
2. What are the culture-bound peculiarities of Ukrainian curses?
3. What expressive means are used to enhance the effect of a cursing utterance?

2. Cursing as an element of conflict talk

Conflict talk attracted attention of scholars long ago. Many researchers have different views of conflict. Social scholars are interested in motives of conflict and how it operates (O'Donnell, Katherine, 1990); studies of linguists contribute to understanding of how language works and try to specify conflict in terms of its pragmatic function (Hugh Lloyd-Jones, 2002). In particular, Kathleen M. Self analyses verbal violence in the medieval narratives of Iceland's conversion to Christianity. The researcher specifies three kinds of verbal violence: a particular sub-genre of insults; coercive speech; and speech as a means of supernatural power (Kathleen M. Self, 2010). The emergence and development of argumentation skills in interpersonal conflict situations are in the focus of Nancy L. Stein and Elizabeth R. Albro (Stein, N. L., & Albro, E. R, 2001). It should be said that conflict is "pervasive and ubiquitous among all living organisms". It is recognized threatening to ourselves and other people as "we expend massive energy and recourses on conflict and attempts to control it at the interpersonal (perhaps intrapersonal), intergroup, and international levels"(Allen D. Grimshaw (ed.), 1990:1). On the other hand, if people perceive it positively and master it appropriately, conflicts can be a helpful force in our lives. So, investigations of conflict talk and its elements may help us to come up closer to understanding conflict as a social process, to reveal the specific ways of manifestation of conflict in different languages and cultures and to find the ways of controlling it.

Because we show our anger, irritation, indignation and other negative emotions through cursing, it can be considered as an element of conflict talk. Cursing permits a curser to express his negative emotions and affect a listener. However, what is a curse?

According to different dictionaries, there is a plenty of definitions for curses. For example, Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English defines them as follows: 1. a swear word or words that you say because you are very angry; 2. a word or sentence used to ask God or a magical power to do something bad to someone or something; 3. something that causes trouble, harm etc. (Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English). Based on Merriam Webster Dictionary, this word means: 1. a prayer or invocation for harm or injury to come upon one; 2. something that is cursed or accursed; 3. evil or misfortune that comes as if in response to imprecation or as retribution; 4. a cause of great harm or misfortune (Merriam Webster Dictionary). In this study, curses are defined as the special offensive formulas intended to set a communicative dominancy over the addressee in the conflict situation.

Cursing as a tradition goes back to ancient times. People believed that curses were inevitably fulfilled. The strong belief in the power of curses made them an effective tool to attain justice, revenge or humiliate an enemy. The major purposes for curses to be thrown were also for protection of homes, treasures and sacred places. They were usually used when the curser had no other means against the person harming him. The harm intended by curses can range from mental and physical disorders, bad luck to even death. An important factor in the effectiveness of a curse was the curser's belief in it as the power of the spoken word was unquestioned in the ancient times. Nowadays cursing has lost its impact and original purpose. Curse words are used on a common basis; in the conflict situation, they substitute physical attacks and may act as a form of verbal aggression, as a means of psychological pressure, an instrument of emotional release.

Cultural and psychological language studies have provided useful approaches to the analysis of cursing. Thus, Evangelos Gr. Avdikos examines the nature of curses as an interesting means of studying local worldview by using specific ethnographic examples from the Greek island of Karpathos. The researcher believes that "every society's main care is to safeguard its cultural capital, perceptions, and social relations as well as its daily and ritual behaviors, which guarantee its cohesion and facilitate its reproduction"(Evangelos Gr. Avdikos, 2011: 88). Daniel Nehrbass studies the nature of anger and hatred in the psalms and highlights some of the redemptive aspects of these emotions (Daniel Nehrbass, 2013). Corinne A. Kratz explores the concept of genres of power through a comparative analysis of blessings, curses and oaths as performed by Okiek in Kenya (Corinne A. Kratz, 1989). The present article examines curses as conflict speech acts marked by cultural specific features and discusses their peculiarities in the Ukrainian cultural context. Curses are considered here as verbal routines spoken in conflict situations under specific conditions.

3. Data analysis

Each nation has developed its own culturally conditioned conflict behavior rules. For example, the Arabs and Hispanics traditionally exhibit emotions freely; restraint and self-control are the virtues of the Finns, Estonians, Chinese, and Japanese. Emotional restraint is also attributed to the British. The original features of the Ukrainians are expressiveness, emotionality, domination of emotional sensual nature over rational. Although curses are found in most cultural conflict traditions around the world and functions performed by them are the same, the content of cursing formulas may vary.

Further, we are going to analyze the examples of cursing speech acts and distinguish their peculiar features rooted in the Ukrainian national culture. The material for analysis was taken from the works of Ukrainian writers, popular collections of proverbs and sayings. For each group a table is drawn.

1

Cursing speech act:	А щоб ти щастя не знав! Бодай тобі добра не було! Бодай тебе побила лиха година та нещаслива! Щоб ти не знав ні щастя, ні долі!
Goal:	to live an unhappy, miserable life

Cultural background:	associated with mythological thinking (mythological images of Happiness and Good/Evil Fate)
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2

Cursing speech act:	А щоб тебе грім побив! Сонце б тебе побило! Щоб тебе понесло по нетрях і болотах! Лети з усіма вихрами! Щоб тебе завійниця узяла!
Goal:	to be damaged by forces of nature
Cultural background:	associated with forces of nature

3

Cursing speech act:	Сіль тобі в око! Сіль тобі в вічі, печина в зуби, а камінь на груди! Сіль тобі в очі, часник на язик! Сіль тобі в вічі, камінь у груди, а печені кошенята в зуби!
Goal:	usually said in order not to be jinxed
Cultural background:	associated with magic rituals

4

Cursing speech act:	А щоб твоя дружинонька з кумом повелася! А щоб тебе люди не знали! Слава б тобі пропала!
Goal:	to be a betrayed husband or to be condemned by society
Cultural background:	associated with social laws, place of a person in society

5

Cursing speech act:	Бодай ти галушки не проковтнув! Щоб ти вдавився! Щоб тебе галушкою вдавило! Бодай тобі кістка в горло!
Goal:	to have problems while eating
Cultural background:	associated with eating traditions and culinary code

6

Cursing speech act:	Бодай тобі ні сходу, ні в почці плоду!
Goal:	not to gather the harvest
Cultural background:	associated with agricultural traditions

7

Cursing speech act:	Щоб тебе татари вбили! Щоб тебе ворог взяв! Щоб тебе орда взяла! А бодай його кримці взяли!
Goal:	to be conquered or killed by enemies
Cultural background:	associated with country's history

8

Cursing speech act:	А бодай тебе чорти вхопили! А бодай ти смоли в пеклі напився! Нехай тебе чорт візьме! Іди під три чорти і чотири відьми! А сто дідьків у твої бебехи та печінки!
Goal:	to bring harm or destruction to a person
Cultural background:	associated with demonology

9

Cursing speech act:	Бодай тебе трясця трясла! А щоб тобі повилазило! Щоб тебе родимець побив! А щоб йому голова облізла! А щоб ти сказився!
Goal:	to cause serious health problems
Cultural background:	associated with widespread illnesses

10

Cursing speech act:	Перун тебе побий! А бий тебе сила Божа! Хрест би тебе Божий побив!
Goal:	to be punished by God
Cultural background:	associated with religion (Pagan and Christian) and religious symbols

11

Cursing speech act:	Ні кола тобі, ні двора, ні рогатого вола!
Goal:	not to have their own farm
Cultural background:	associated with housing traditions

12

Cursing speech act:	Щоб тебе піп не ховав! Щоб тебе земля не прийняла! О щоб йому ні дна, ні покришки!
Goal:	not to die or to be buried
Cultural background:	associated with burial ritual

13

Cursing speech act:	Чорт би вашого батька взяв! Матері твоїй трясця! А матері твоїй хрін!
Goal:	to do harm to opponent's parents
Cultural background:	associated with the honourable status of mother/father

14

Cursing speech act:	Щоб ти не діждав гречаної паски їсти!
Goal:	to die before a holiday
Cultural background:	associated with national holidays and festivals

15

Cursing speech act:	Цур тобі, пек! Цур та пек лихим очам!
Goal:	usually said to get rid of an annoying person
Cultural background:	associated with family cult

16

Cursing speech act:	Бодай його корінь зівся! Бодай його кодро з накоренком перевелось!
Goal:	not to have offsprings
Cultural background:	associated with family values

17

Cursing speech act:	Бодай-єс дівувала до сивої коси! Бодай-сь тоді мала вінець, як світу буде кінець!
Goal:	not to get married (for girls)
Cultural background:	associated with wedding traditions

Cursing speech act:	Щоб тебе калачі побили і макітра з пирогами! Щоб тебе муха вбрикнула!
Goal:	to do harm but not actually
Cultural background:	associated with national humor

4. Discussion

4.1. Groups

In this study, all cursing speech acts were classified into the groups closely associated with country's culture, traditions, customs, history, mythology, superstitions and religion. Issues of death, destruction, misfortune, health and other problems can be seen in almost all curses. Through some curses, a curser appeals to God, forces of nature, mythological creatures and asks them to cause some trouble to a hearer, e.g. to get fever. They do not have full English equivalents; they seem meaningful for the native speakers only and cannot be explained without the same cultural background. Moreover, Ukrainian curses used in conflict talk are highly metaphorical; the intended meaning cannot be interpreted word by word. In fact, most of them should be considered as idiomatic expressions. For example, to understand the utterance “Цур тобі, пек!” one must be aware of house cult and house guards named Tsur (Chur) and Peck who, as people believed, protected the family from danger. “Щоб тебе татари вбили!” – reminds us about the period in Ukraine's history when the Mongols and Tatars conquered and plundered some parts of the country.

Thus, curses occupy a certain place in the Ukrainian communicative code as speech behaviour stereotypes and reflect the specificity of the national language consciousness.

4.2. Functions

Most commonly shared functions of curses are as follows: emotional, axiological, pedagogical, therapeutic, identifying, manipulative, influential, etc. The functions of cursing speech acts in conflict talk serve mostly psychological and sociocultural goals: they let us to express our negative feelings and emotions about others. In particular, the use of abusive cursing formulas in conflict talk leads to the communicative imbalance, lower social status of the recipient, weakening of his communicative positions, strengthening of negative emotions, absorption of emotions experienced by an addresser, etc. Communicative functions of cursing formulas are practically unlimited and manifested only in the situation of communication. Our suggestion in the article is that cursing speech acts become meaningful only in full context. It is also worth saying that more than one function can be performed by the same curse.

4.3. Expressive means

In order to make a curse sound more persuasive and significant a curser use different means of expressiveness at all levels of the Ukrainian language: phonetic, morphological, word-building, lexical and syntactical. For the purpose of logical and emotional intensification of the curse the following means are most frequently used:

- constant epithets: *Нехай тебе **свѣта** земля не прийме!*

- similes: *Щоб ти скапався, як роса на сонці! А щоб ти так хліба їла, як щиру правду говорила!*

- metaphors: *А сміявся б ти на кутні зуби!*

- rude forms (face-muzzle): *А щоб твоєю мордою просо молотили!*

- diminutive suffixes: *Допусти, Господоньку, на нього грім із ясного неба! Земленька би свята тебе не прийняла!*

- numerals to enhance and multiply the effect: *Іди під три чорти і чотири відьми! Бодай йому три рази по сім разів біда була!*

- particles: *хай, нехай (най), бодай, щоб(и), аби*

- antonymic constructions: *Бодай здорова була та назад не встала! Дай, Боже, здоров'я, щоб і дихати нікуди!*

- rhymes and alliteration: *Прийшов з лісу – іди собі к бісу! Бодай тобі добро поза кожне ребро!*

- repetition of words: *Цур тобі, пек тобі, осина тобі!*

Thus, Ukrainian curses is a remarkable linguistic phenomenon; they are known for their impressive and creative nature.

5. Conclusion

In every language community there are accepted rules that determine how people use the language and perform communicative acts appropriate to particular situations. As the current study shows the Ukrainian language is rich in curse expressions. They are uttered in conflict situations under specific conditions as a sign of anger, hatred, irritation or unfair treatment. The intensity of negative emotions in cursing speech acts is much higher than in other speech acts that makes curses a substantial element of conflict talk.

In addition to the emotional meaning, cursing speech acts include cultural meaning, too. It has been shown that most Ukrainian curses are closely connected to country's culture, traditions, customs, history, mythology, superstitions and religion.

Communicative functions of cursing formulas are understood from the context in which they are said. Like any speech acts, curses subject to the basic laws of communication, they are the means of verbal communication, self-promotion and manipulation. The role of curses in conflict situation is to demonstrate negative emotional reactions such as anger or hatred or inability to use physical force. By uttering curses a curser relieves his feelings and calms down psychologically.

Some Ukrainian curses are stated directly, the others are implied (a curser may ask God or forces of nature to carry out the punishment). The peculiarity of most Ukrainian curses is their expressiveness. To make a curse sound more persuasive a curser use similes, epithets, metaphors, diminutive suffixes, numerals, rude forms, particles, antonymic constructions, rhymes and alliteration, repetition of words and other means of expressiveness.

In conclusion, curses are considered as important markers of national speech behavior reflecting cultural customs and traditions and existing as verbal stereotyped routines. Further research in this area will reveal other specific features of Ukrainian cursing formulas that will contribute to better understanding the national character and way of Ukrainian thinking.

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